

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE UNDER GLOBALIZATION

Jumanazarov Sirozhiddin Salaydinovich

A.National Institute of pedagogical skills named after Avloni
head of the department, Ph.D., associate professor
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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada globallashuv sharoitida umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi "Tarbiya" fani o'qituvchilarining uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlantirishni pedagogik shartlari keltirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: globallashuv, tarbiya, pedagogik shart, uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlantirish, monitoring, raqamli texnologiya, mobil texnologiya.

Abstract. This article presents the pedagogical conditions for the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education" of a general secondary school in the context of globalization.

Keywords: globalization, education, pedagogical skills, continuous professional development, monitoring, digital technology, mobile technology.

In the system of continuous education, adherence to pedagogical conditions is of great importance for the effective organization of the educational and upbringing process [1, 2]. Properly selected and systematically implemented pedagogical conditions allow the teacher to achieve high results in practical work with students at different stages of education [3]. Therefore, it is advisable to adhere to pedagogical conditions in the educational process, including the continuous professional development of school teachers, and, if necessary, to improve them.

Therefore, within the framework of the study, the following pedagogical conditions for the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education" were identified:

The first pedagogical condition: development of the professional value-motivational component of teachers of the subject "Education". The implementation of this pedagogical condition includes familiarizing teachers of the subject "Education" of general secondary schools with the main values. This involves helping teachers of the subject "Education" to choose a system of values that is of personal importance and, on this basis, forming appropriate professional pedagogical motivation, as a result of which an active pedagogical position and a value-based attitude are achieved.

Second pedagogical condition: Use of digital technologies in the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education". This pedagogical condition envisages the continuous development of the skills and competence of teachers of the subject "Education" through the use of digital technologies.

The third pedagogical condition: Development of the design competence of teachers of the subject "Education" using digital technologies. At the moment, the problems of reforms in the system of continuous professional development are related to the development of the competence of pedagogical personnel in designing lessons. The results of observation and analysis show that the professional competence of school teachers lags behind the requirements of rapidly developing educational processes. This situation indicates the relevance of the problems associated with the development of the design competence of students in the process of continuous professional development [4]. Therefore, the development of new approaches to developing the competence of school teachers in designing lessons in the system of continuous professional development, the formation and development of their professional competence has become a requirement of the time [5]. In this regard, the use of digital technologies, including information and educational environments, educational portals and educational websites, and cloud services is considered effective.

The fourth pedagogical condition: Monitoring the professional development of teachers of the subject "Education". The nature of monitoring teachers of the subject "Education" in the system of continuous professional development is the management of this process, which consists in a targeted, coordinated impact on it in terms of supporting it by implementing the functions of collecting information, analyzing, planning, organizing and managing it. Monitoring the continuous professional activity of teachers, choosing the content and forms of their professional development activities is carried out through various instructions, analysis of teachers' results, certification, etc. Therefore, in the system of continuous professional development, one of the conditions for improving the professional skills of teachers in the subject "Education" is to determine the direction of teachers' professional development, to ensure the continuity, effectiveness and control of this process, to develop and implement a program for monitoring the professional development of teachers, using the following principles:

- the accuracy of the criteria, manifested in the selection of criteria for studying the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the object under study, and their reliance;

- the inclusion of the selection of the content and methods, tools and forms of improving the monitoring object based on diagnostics and prognosis;

- corrections, including the reformulation of goals and the introduction into operation in the event of deviations or negative trends in the development of the object.

Fifth pedagogical condition: Use of mobile technologies in the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education". The use of mobile technologies in the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education" has a number of advantages, in particular, virtual education in the subject, keeping abreast of news, self-assessment, etc. Therefore, the use of this technology in the continuous professional development of teachers of the subject "Education" is considered effective.

Thus, it is considered appropriate to follow the pedagogical conditions proposed in the research in the continuous professional development of "Education" teachers. Based on these, it will be possible for "Education" teachers to effectively design and organize lessons in an interesting way.

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